

Demonstration of Visual Displays

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Executive summary

This document serves as the report about demos addressing Visual Displays. We describe the system and actions developed by VBW to address requirements for Visual Displays in combination with haptics and auditory displays. The work for this deliverable was initially part of WP4 but firstly there were no person months associated to that task, and the work overlapped to a large degree with work that was carried out in WP3. Therefore, in this deliverable we describe the setups that were developed for studies and demos that exploit the developed functionalities.

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
ECG	Electrocardiogram
EEG	Electroencephalogram
EOG	Electrooculogram
HRTF	Head Related Transfer Function
IK	Inverse Kinematics
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
PAHRE	Prueba Auditiva de Habla en Ruido <i>in Español</i>
SDK	Software Development Kit
HA/HL	Hearing Aid/Hearing Loss
SOFA	Spatially Oriented Format for Acoustics
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

Introduction

This document serves as the report for demos that demonstrate Visual Displays in virtual and augmented environments. Based on the requirements of WP4 and WP5, VBW has integrated several technologies to study the impact of multimodal stimuli.

As detailed in D3.3, VBW has designed an API that enables developers to deliver multi modal stimuli to participants of experiences. This API can be used by the Guest system to control visual, auditory and haptic aspects of a shared experience. Here we provide details of the functionalities that were required to setup and carry out an EEG study to investigate the effects of co-presence on an image memory task.

This setup is also available as a demo experience and serves as our first demo experience for this deliverable. The second demonstration is a setup for a study that investigates the possible improvement in auditory understanding by sensory addition through voice coil haptics and lip-sync including the simulation of hearing loss and hearing aids as designed for T5.2 of WP5.

Content

The document is divided into subsections first describing the requirements for the setup to study effects of co-presence. We give details on the setup and the details of the developed system which comprises of an EEG capturing system, a PC that coordinates the triggering of stimuli and capturing of data and 2 XR headsets that track participants head, hand, face and eye movements and provide the visual and auditory stimuli of the shared VR experience.

Secondly, we describe the demonstration of a preliminary setup for a study to investigate the improvement of comprehension from audio using voice coil haptics of consumer devices in a VR scenario. We will give details about the commands developed to carry out haptic rendering using the controllers of consumer VR headsets and the integration.

Both Demonstrations are also illustrated in a video available at: <https://youtu.be/tqteGraw4KA>

The video is also available on GuestXR's YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@GuestXR>

1 List of Demonstrations

Demonstration 1: Setup for the Study on impact of copresence on an image memory task

In this section we describe the setup developed for a study on the impact of social presence while embodied in a full body avatar. We compare three conditions, 1) being with another person represented by another avatar, 2) being with a computer-controlled avatar or 3) being alone with no other avatar in the environment. The setup is also described in more detail in a master thesis by Zeynep Yenigün in [1].

This work aims to deepen our understanding of how virtual social support through avatars can influence stress responses and cognitive performance, potentially enhancing emotional regulation and social competencies in virtual settings. Brain activity, eye, face and body-movements, heart rate, and behavioural responses can be recorded and prepared for analysis.

For this study, we employed embodiment in life size full body avatars which are rendered by standalone headsets. Whole body movements were inferred from hand and head tracking based on inverse kinematics. Image stimuli in the shared environment were generated by OpenAI’s DALL E 3¹ system with image prompts generated by OpenAI’s GPT4o². Four out of the 240 example images are shown in *Figure 1*.

¹ DALL-E 3. OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/dall-e-3/>

² Hello GPT-4o. OpenAI. 13.05.24. <https://openai.com/index/hello-gpt-4o/>

Figure 1 Example stimuli images of the 240 images that were generated by dall-e3 based on prompts generated by GPT4o

We capture EEG, ECG and EOG signals while the participant experiences the VR scenario. Details of the electrode placements are given in *Figure 5*. Example images from the environment are shown in *Figure 2* and *Figure 3*.

Figure 2 The VR office environment in which the experiment took place.

Figure 3 Three female avatars were used in this study: the one on the left represents the computer-controlled avatar, the one in the middle represents the real person's avatar, and the one on the right represents the participant themselves.

A participant being donned the HMD and interacting with the VR environment while wearing the EEG, ECG, and EOG electrodes is show in *Figure 4*.

Figure 4 Left: Participant wearing EEG cap and EOG electrodes is being donned a Meta's Quest Pro device. Right: Participant wearing electrodes and HMD interacts with VR through hand movements.

Figure 5 EEG, EOG and ECG electrodes are used to capture these data in the study

Demonstration 2: Setup for a VR Study on the improvement of auditory understanding through voice coil haptics

In collaboration between VBW, Eurecat and the Baruch Ivcher Institute at Reichman University we have developed a setup with the aim of investigating the improvements in the recognition of words by adding pulse code modulated haptics to audio recordings played back, similar to the work described in [2], [3]. We plan to adapt the methodology used in [4].

We have added functionality to the GuestXR framework developed at VBW that enables us to play haptic sequences derived from audio through Meta's Haptics Studio³ through a command. A screenshot of the haptic studio is shown in Figure 6.

In a pilot study we aim to test the setup first with participants with good hearing and then with participants with hearing impairments. For the first set of participants with good hearing we added the possibility to simulate the effects of hearing loss or a hearing aid by adding the HL/HA simulator of the 3DTuneIn package⁴ that was previously developed by the consortium members of SONICOM, a sister project.

Figure 6 Meta's haptics studio provides parameters to finetune the conversion from audio to haptics description.

The system performs 3D audio spatialisation by using the SteamAudio system⁵ which also has the ability to simulate the head related transfer function (HRTF) described as Spatially Oriented Format for Acoustics (SOFA) files⁶, that we can add to each experience individually to simulate the acoustic effects of ear and body shape of the participant's avatar.

³ Haptics Studio. Meta Horizon. <https://developers.meta.com/horizon/resources/haptics-studio/>

⁴ Unity Wrapper for 3D-Tune-In Toolkit. https://github.com/3DTune-In/3dti_AudioToolkit_UnityWrapper

⁵ Steam Audio 4.6.0. <https://github.com/ValveSoftware/steam-audio>

⁶ SOFA (Spatially Oriented Format for Acoustics) <https://www.sofaconventions.org/>

In addition, we have added functionality to enable and disable the lip-sync that would be carried out by default when playing back audio on an avatar so that the avatars lips would move as if it was speaking the audio. We are considering using lip-sync as an additional variable for the study on speech reception to identify if it can contribute to the improvement of understanding.

Figure 7 shows a screenshot of an example experience in which the participant can choose from 4 buttons to replay audio through the avatar alone or in combination with HA/HL simulation or haptics or both.

Figure 7 Screenshot from a demo experience that shows the possibilities of playing audio on an avatar in combination with HA/HL simulation and/or haptics voice coil rendering.

Conclusions

This document serves as the report for the demos to demonstrate the multimodal capabilities of the developed system.

Two demos are described, one that investigates the effects of social presence during a memory task and the other describes a demo for a setup for a study that will be carried out in 2025 on the impact of haptics derived from audio on speech understanding.

Both demos show how the set of actions that the Guest can perform from a Python client can change aspects of the environment visually, haptics or through sounds or change of aspects of a participant's hearing through the simulation of effects of hearing loss or the use of hearing aids.

References

- [1] Z. Yenigün, "Bodies in Interaction – a Combined VR and EEG Study," Maastricht University, Brain and Emotion Lab, Maastricht University, 2024.
- [2] K. Ciesla, T. Wolak, A. Lorens, H. Skarżyński, and A. Amedi, "Speech-to-touch sensory substitution: a 10-decibel improvement in speech-in-noise understanding after a short training," *Res Sq*, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-429202/v1.
- [3] A. Snir, K. Cieśła, R. Vekslar, and A. Amedi, "Highly compromised auditory spatial perception in aided congenitally hearing-impaired and rapid improvement with tactile technology," *iScience*, vol. 27, no. 9, p. 110808, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.isci.2024.110808.
- [4] M. Rodríguez-Ferreiro, M. Durán-Bouza, and V. Marrero-Aguiar, "Analysis of the Spanish Auditory Test of Speech in Noise (PAHRE) in a Population with Hearing Loss," *Audiol Res*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 861–874, 2024, doi: 10.3390/audiolres14050073.